

Buddying as a Transformative Tool in Intersectional Social Work: Innovation in Student Training and Support of At-Risk Children¹

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Abstract

OBJECTIVES: Article explores how student-led buddying can function as a transformative tool in intersectional social work education and practice. It focuses on supporting children at risk of social exclusion and fostering students' reflective and ethical development. **THEORETICAL BASE:** Article is grounded in international and Czech conceptualisations of buddying as a structured, supportive, peer relationship as transformative learning theory, as a process of changing frames of reference through experience. It also frames the intervention within the context of structural child poverty and exclusion in the Czech Republic, includes intersectionality as a lens to understand multiple, overlapping disadvantages. **METHODS:** The study is based on a qualitative analysis of interviews with students and practitioners engaged in a pilot buddying programme. While children's lived experiences were accessed indirectly, the data reflect students' perceptions of children's intersecting disadvantages and their professional engagement with these realities. **OUTCOMES:** Buddying offers dual benefits: relational and emotional support for children, and a reflective, experience-based learning environment for students. Journaling and supervision were identified as key tools in navigating power dynamics, systemic barriers, and students' own professional identities. **SOCIAL WORK IMPLICATIONS:** The findings support integrating buddying and reflective tools into social work education, and call for institutional shifts toward more collaborative, ethically grounded, and equity-focused social work practice.

Keywords

buddying, reflective practice, intersectionality, transformative learning, at-risk youth, social work education, peer support

INTRODUCTION

The divide between social work practice and the academic domain, where theoretical discourse predominates, is a recurring theme in educational research and a characteristic feature of social work itself (Fook, Gardner, 2007). A lack of critical self-reflection in practice is sometimes attributed to the professional pressure to have all the answers and the desire to avoid the discomfort of not knowing (Pack, 2011).

This disconnection is particularly evident in the field education of social work students, who often describe experiencing "practice shock", a response to the dissonance between the ideals of social work instilled during their studies and the complexities of real-world practice (Glumbíková, 2021). At the same time, research focused on the needs of children at risk of social exclusion indicates that, beyond the lack of adequate housing, the primary unmet needs of homeless children are relational, specifically the need for emotional support and secure attachments (see e.g., Glumbíková, Mikulec, 2021). Despite this, there is currently no project, either in the Czech Republic or abroad, that bridges the gap between the need for reflective integration of theory and practice in social work education and the relational needs of children facing social exclusion.

Integrating the concept of buddying into the practical training of social work students has the potential to bring meaningful benefits, both for the target group of children and for the professional development of students. Through this collaborative process, both vulnerable children and students may develop similar competencies, such as empowerment, self-efficacy, social and intercultural skills, organisational and communication abilities, language proficiency, and personal growth.

The aim of the article is therefore to explore how student-led buddying can function as a transformative tool in intersectional social work education and practice. It focuses on supporting children at risk of social exclusion and fostering students' reflective and ethical development.

Children and Youth at Risk of Social Exclusion in the Czech Republic

There are no precise or up-to-date figures on the number of children living in socially excluded localities in the Czech Republic, as the definition of such localities varies and comprehensive statistical data are not always available. In 2019, the Czech government developed the *Strategy for the Prevention of Social Exclusion for the Period 2019–2023*, which estimated the number of people living in socially excluded localities at between 80,000 and 120,000. However, this estimate refers to the total population of these areas and not specifically to children.

Current data on the number of children living in socially excluded localities in the Moravian-Silesian Region (MSR) are also lacking. Nonetheless, several organisations and projects working with children and youth in socially excluded localities within the MSR provide estimated figures. For instance, the *Otevřená náruč* (“Open Arms”) project estimated that approximately 10,000 children and adolescents were living in socially excluded localities in the MSR in 2021. This figure, however, remains an approximation.

The city of Ostrava is one of the MSR’s municipalities that can unequivocally be characterised as post-industrial. The city’s historical development was driven by the emergence of new industrial sectors, which led to the construction of worker colonies and housing estates. The industrial restructuring of the 1990s brought significant structural and social changes, including rising unemployment and the emergence of so-called “brownfields”, which today make up as much as one-third of the city’s area. According to the *Strategic Plan for Social Inclusion in Ostrava 2015–2018*, there were 9 socially excluded or socially vulnerable localities in Ostrava in 2006; by 2015, this number had risen to 15⁶ with a population of 6,520. The same document also notes that vulnerable groups include individuals receiving social security benefits, specifically housing allowance and supplementary housing benefit. Based on data on the number of people affected by these benefits, it is estimated that between 30,000 and 35,000 individuals in Ostrava are impacted. It is important to note that these benefits do not affect only individuals but often entire households (Statutory city of Ostrava, 2015).

Another important source for mapping social exclusion in Ostrava is the *Map of Socially Excluded Localities and Residential Segregation*, which reports that there are a total of 264 settlement units in the city. Of these, 46 exhibit a higher degree of social exclusion: 28 were classified as having a medium level, 7 as high, and 11 as extreme. While some socially excluded localities are relatively well located, others are highly segregated and lack basic civic infrastructure, such as shops, healthcare services, adequate public transportation, or schools (SMO, 2017).

Social exclusion arises through the interplay of multiple, interrelated factors. These include material poverty, high levels of indebtedness, dependence on social welfare, insecure or substandard housing, the prevalence of risky behaviours and criminality, high rates of migration, long-term unemployment, and limited access to quality education (Švec, 2010; PROCES, 2015; Statutory city of Ostrava, 2018). The cumulative effect of these factors significantly impedes individuals and families from achieving meaningful social integration, effectively excluding them from broader society (Statutory city of Ostrava, 2018).

Due to their spatial isolation, socially excluded localities (SELs) also constitute a barrier to accessing basic institutions such as social networks and educational opportunities (MSK, 2021). In the domain of education, it is worth noting that the vast majority of SEL residents attain only primary education at best. The education system itself is often viewed as a mechanism for the intergenerational transmission of social exclusion. Low educational attainment subsequently limits access to stable employment, resulting in reliance on precarious, short-term contracts with low wages or even engagement in informal or illegal work. This exposes individuals to both economic and social insecurity (GAC, 2015; MSK, 2021).

⁶ Ostrava is administratively divided into 23 city districts, with socially excluded localities situated in six of them: Mariánské Hory and Hulváky, Moravská Ostrava and Přívoz, Poruba, Radvanice and Bartovice, Slezská Ostrava, and Vítkovice.

Data from GAC (2015) indicate that approximately 22% (an estimated 3,000–3,500 individuals in the Czech Republic) of students growing up in SELs are educated in ethnically homogeneous schools. The placement of pupils into such institutions leads to the formation of so-called “segregated schools” (Truhlářová, Smutek, 2006). This segregation often correlates with problematic student behaviour. Early school leaving is typically linked to social environmental factors, including peer influence, lack of social competencies, insufficient parental support, and negative perceptions from the broader community. These conditions create obstacles to school enrolment, academic persistence, and overall motivation to continue education. Other contributing factors include household responsibilities, early pregnancy, difficulties adapting to new school environments, financial barriers to education, undervaluation of schooling and its applicability, poor literacy skills, and repeated academic failure, all of which can result in chronic absenteeism.

Children raised in contexts of social exclusion frequently lack access to roles and values that would support their integration into mainstream society. Instead, they may adopt behavioural patterns that further entrench their marginalisation and poverty. Often, these children develop coping mechanisms suited to life in excluded environments—mechanisms that, however, are dysfunctional or maladaptive within majority societal norms (GAC, 2015; MSR, 2021).

Housing plays a critical role in shaping the social environment. Prolonged residence in inadequate conditions undermines individuals’ social mobility and limits opportunities for socialisation, especially given the closed, segregated nature of such environments, the socioeconomic composition of residents, and prevailing attitudes and perceptions of life chances. This frequently leads to the intergenerational transmission of disadvantage and the replication of specific life trajectories.

Housing quality also significantly affects children’s educational outcomes and school-related problems (e.g., bullying, poor academic performance). Adverse housing conditions are typically characterised by overcrowding and lack of privacy, excessive housing cost burdens, and residential instability marked by frequent relocations. These factors are closely associated with grade repetition and academic underachievement. Poor housing conditions have also been shown to reduce the likelihood of admission to a preferred secondary school—although not necessarily to a university, where parental educational attainment is a stronger predictor (Median, 2017).

THEORETICAL BASE

This text is grounded in three core conceptual axes that underpin our research:

A) Transformative Learning Theory; B) Intersectionality; C) The Ethics of Care framework.

Given the above foundations and the conceptual orientation of the article, it is essential to articulate its theoretical framework. This study draws on a combination of theoretical frameworks that provide conceptual grounding for understanding buddying as a transformative, relational, and ethically engaged practice. *Transformative Learning Theory*, as originally posited by Mezirow in 1991, posits that learning is a profound process that revolves around critical reflection and the revision of one’s beliefs and assumptions. This theoretical approach is particularly relevant in understanding buddying, where students often navigate complex and unfamiliar social landscapes that challenge their pre-existing notions. Scholars such as Cranton (2006) have emphasized that through these “disorienting dilemmas,” students can achieve a more nuanced and critically reflective professional identity (Finnegan, 2019; Alam, 2022). This theory has been further explored in the context of diverse educational environments, indicating that not only does transformative learning facilitate personal growth, but it also serves as a catalyst for social change, fostering a collective consciousness that acknowledges and responds to systemic inequities (Hatlevik, 2018). Recent literature further confirms this perspective. Jones (2015) emphasises the value of transformative learning in social work education for helping students engage with uncertainty, discomfort, and the ethics of real-world complexity, thus strengthening their critical and moral agency. The

combination of transformative learning and ethical engagement underlines the potential for budding to extend beyond mere academic support and cultivate a moral imperative toward social justice and community responsibility (Finnegan, 2019).

Intersectionality, a concept provides a critical framework for understanding and analysing how multiple overlapping dimensions of disadvantage and privilege impact lived experiences (Magrizos, Roumpi, 2020). In the context of budding, recognizing the intersectionality of factors such as socio-economic status, ethnicity, and familial background allows for a more comprehensive understanding of how these elements shape the interactions between students and their clients. Collins and Bilge (2016) highlight that such an analytical lens accentuates the ways in which students' positionalities influence their practice, prompting a reflexive engagement that seeks to dismantle hegemonic narratives. Moreover, the integration of intersectionality into the budding process fosters a socially just approach that challenges superficial engagement with clients. This reflects the view of Simon et al. (2021), who call for intersectionality in social work education to move beyond identity-based categorisations and instead address shared roots of structural disadvantage and privilege. In our study, intersectionality was also operationalised in the formulation of interview prompts and in our sensitivity to layered disadvantages as perceived by students. The implementation of intersectional frameworks encourages students to critically examine their roles and responsibilities, thus enhancing their capacity for ethical decision-making and relational understanding in practice (Ramvi, Hellstrand, Jensen et al., 2023). Finally, *The Ethics of Care framework* presents a paradigm that prioritizes attentiveness, responsibility, and responsiveness in relational practices. This framework is invaluable for interpreting budding, as it positions caring not simply as a transactional engagement but as a deeply interconnected relational process that emphasizes reciprocity and ethical considerations in relationships (Buchanan, Newnham, Ireson et al., 2022). The findings from Buchanan et al. (2022) further substantiate the importance of applying care ethics within healthcare modalities, emphasizing the role of relational practices that enhance ethical sensitivity and moral responsibility. Complementing this, McAuliffe (2023) underscores the relevance of care ethics in social work practice as a context-responsive, relational framework for ethical judgement, especially in interactions with vulnerable clients. In practice, an ethics of care approach within budding frameworks promotes emotional openness, trust, and the effective establishment of boundaries to ensure safety and ethical engagement. This underlines the necessity of supervision and institutional support, which serve as foundational pillars in sustaining ethically sound care relationships (Houbeish, 2021). As such, budding can be viewed as an exercise in relational ethics, fostering mutual growth and development within educational environments.

In the context of our research, intersectionality served not only as an analytical lens but also as a guiding principle in the design and interpretation of the study. The diversity of participants—social work students, and practitioners—reflected our commitment to exploring how structural inequalities intersect in lived experiences. Interview prompts were designed to capture how multiple axes of disadvantage (e.g., poverty, ethnicity, institutional exclusion) shape both the needs of children and the reflective development of students. Thematic analysis was informed by intersectional sensitivity, enabling us to trace how students perceived, navigated, and responded to these overlapping forms of marginalisation in their professional roles.

Furthermore, we conceptualised budding not only as a supportive intervention, but also as a pedagogical site for professionalisation in social work education. Drawing on theories of professional identity formation (Dornan et al., 2007; Trede, Macklin, Bridges, 2012), we view the budding process as a situated learning experience where students engage with real-world ethical dilemmas, relational tensions, and power asymmetries. These encounters foster reflexivity, emotional resilience, and the development of a professional self. Through regular supervision and journaling, budding offers a structured yet relationally rich space in which social work students can internalise professional values and ethical orientations central to the field. This professionalisation

process is not linear but emerges dialogically in response to the children's realities, institutional contexts, and students' own positionalities.

STUDENT BUDDYING AS A TOOL FOR SUPPORTING INTEGRATION

The integration of reflective practice into social work education is well established in pedagogical literature. The persistent gap between the domain of practice and the academic sphere, where theoretical discourse unfolds, has been widely documented and is considered a defining feature of the profession (Kember, Jones, Loke et al., 1996; Platzer, Snelling, Blake, 1997). This disconnection is often reinforced by students' reluctance to engage in critical self-reflection—stemming from the perceived pressure to demonstrate certainty and avoid the discomfort of not knowing (Pack, 2011). In response, a variety of tools have been developed to foster reflexivity. Pack (2014), for example, explored the use of multimedia technologies to support students' self-reflection when working with complex practice cases, highlighting the need for innovative pedagogical approaches tailored to emotionally demanding contexts.

Globally, online reflective journals have been incorporated into the curriculum of many universities—including several ranked among the world's top ten by the Times Higher Education World University Rankings 2023. Despite their potential, these tools often lack customisability, as they are not developed in-house by the universities, limiting educators' ability to align them with discipline-specific pedagogical goals. Additionally, existing platforms are rarely designed with the distinct needs of social work field education in mind, nor do they facilitate two-way reflective exchange with clients—in this context, children and youth at risk of social exclusion. The lack of Czech-language versions further impedes their accessibility for students, especially given the emotional and conceptual difficulty of reflective writing (Pack, 2011).

The reflective component of this initiative is embedded within a broader framework of **student buddying**, which is here conceptualised as a structured, reciprocal, and supportive relationship between a social work student and a child or adolescent at risk of social exclusion. Drawing on the work of Campbell (2015), McAllister, Harold, Ahmedani, et al. (2009), and Waddell and Dunn (2005), buddying is defined as a developmental partnership that promotes learning, skills acquisition, and psychosocial support for the less experienced participant through the involvement of a more experienced peer.

Informed by previous mentoring and peer-support models, this approach emphasises the sustained, relational, and educational character of buddying. While the concept of mentoring in social work education is not new, the configuration adopted here is characterised by its long-term orientation and integration into students' reflective practice. In particular, this model aligns with approaches described by Lewis (2018) and Roberts and Birmingham (2017), which view mentoring as a relational tool for addressing individual challenges and needs, rather than simply transmitting knowledge or skills.

Some of these needs are pre-identified through previous therapeutic work with the children, conducted by one of the project's professional partners (Institut prevence, z.s.). This practice underscores the importance of continuity and trust in student-child interactions, particularly during periods of transition, where sustained relational engagement supports the child's ongoing motivation and development.

Within such relationships, the student-buddy can contribute to the child's emotional wellbeing, strengthen self-confidence and self-esteem, and support the development of communication skills and healthy coping strategies. The potential of buddying to serve as a preventive mechanism has also been noted—helping to reduce the likelihood of engagement in risky behaviours such as bullying, substance use, or delinquency by offering alternative, prosocial experiences.

Nevertheless, meaningful engagement with children at risk of social exclusion requires specific competencies and safeguards. For this reason, buddying must be situated within a broader

pedagogical and ethical infrastructure. This is ensured through the collaboration between educators from the Faculty of Social Studies at the University of Ostrava (FSS OU), field supervisors, and practitioners from the Institut prevence. The co-designed online reflective journal serves as a central tool in this ecosystem, enabling structured reflection, documentation of field learning, and the generation of materials for students' practice portfolios, which may be further utilised for final examinations or job interviews.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a participatory action research (PAR) framework tailored to its transformative aims. The aim of this study was to explore how student-led budding functions as a transformative practice in the context of intersectional social work, particularly focusing on its dual impact: providing support to children at risk of social exclusion and contributing to the reflective and ethical development of social work students. The initial phase focused on mapping the needs of children and youth through qualitative data collection, utilizing methods such as individual interviews (a total of 15 interviews), in the period May to December 2024. The selection of communication partners prioritized diversity, ensuring a rich representation of perspectives (Peddle, 2021), including 4 social work students directly involved in budding with children, 6 professionals representing NGOs and public agencies working with socially excluded children and youth, 2 academic educators in social work with a focus on practical training. This composition ensured triangulation across educational, organisational, and experiential dimensions of budding, allowing for richer contextual interpretation. This engagement is central to fostering inclusivity and collective inquiry (Steihaug, Johannessen, Ådnanes, et al., 2016). As for data analyses technique, we conducted thematic analysis as proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006), allowing us to identify and interpret patterns in the qualitative data effectively (Unger, Huber, Kühner et al., 2022). The data were open-coded and then grouped into specific topics (i.e., content-meaning units in the data) based on their similarity or difference. We used Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis because it is based on constructivist principles of working with data, which it considers interpretatively co-created in the interaction between the researcher and the informant. Additionally, cyclical reflection and continuous feedback ensured that all participant groups were involved in data collection. Before the start of the research, all communication partners were informed about the research topic and its purpose (intention). The main principles of ethical conduct in research include obtaining informed consent (Hendl, 2016). Research was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (1964, as amended in World Medical Association, 2013). All human participants were treated with dignity and respect, and the preparation of the manuscript was guided by the ethical principles of the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE). In line with the ethical standards of the Faculty of Social Studies at the University of Ostrava, the research received ethical approval. All participants, including social work students, educators, and practitioners, were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any stage. Data were anonymized, stored securely on university servers, and access was restricted to authorized researchers. The study adhered to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (1964, as amended in World Medical Association, 2013).

The article presents findings from the initial phase of research, highlighting the lived experiences and insights shared by students and practitioners during the participatory mapping process. The effort to achieve the greatest possible validity of the data was made with the knowledge that the data in the research is shaped by the mutual interaction of the researcher and the research participants (Finlay, Gough, 2003), therefore the data itself and the process of obtaining it were cyclically subjected to reflection in all parts of the research (Bradbury-Jones, 2007). Control and monitoring of one's own influence on research was carried out by: a) long-term presence in the research environment (the research was carried out for one year); b) choosing the least intrusive

and most natural data collection techniques (interview in a natural environment, anonymous questionnaire); c) use of triangulation of several research techniques and triangulation of analyses; and d) the effort to actively involve people with lived experience in shaping research.

Despite the richness of the qualitative data, several limitations must be acknowledged. The study used purposive sampling, which, while appropriate for exploratory and context-sensitive research, limits generalisability. The relatively small sample size and context-specific setting constrain the transferability of findings to other populations or institutional environments. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data from students and practitioners may introduce subjective bias. While triangulation and reflexive strategies were employed to enhance credibility, the absence of direct accounts from children themselves restricts the depth of insight into their lived experiences. These limitations should be considered when interpreting the results and implications.

RESULTS

Social Work with Families Experiencing Intersecting Hardships

Communication partners emphasize the importance of understanding the broader context in which children grow up. They point out that a child's behaviour, needs, and capacities are closely linked to their living conditions and social environment: *"...if you want to find something out about the kid, you have to go out to them, you have to go to the environment where they're growing up, then you'll understand a lot, you'll know who is in front of you and what their possibilities are. That's where you understand the most..."* (KP2). *"I get to know their whole environment, I kind of live with them..."* (KP8). *"...whether they go to school, how they're doing, whether they're coping with the relocation, or how they perceive it, whether they ever had their own room, their own space, how many siblings they have, and how they're managing these situations, when families had to move multiple times, or when there was domestic violence or other violence against the parents"* (KP3). Understanding children's lives requires attention to the complexity and interrelatedness of social factors such as poverty, family instability, and limited access to supportive services. Social workers and students encountering children in practice must navigate and interpret these overlapping vulnerabilities as part of their professional engagement. The participants also stress the importance of involving the entire family system in support processes. Strengthening the family as a whole can have a positive ripple effect on the child's development and well-being: *"There should be more work with the family, but earlier on, not at this age. We see that the children who come to us, at around 15 years old, no longer listen to their parents, because they usually went through something negative with them. I think if this had been addressed when they were around 8, or even earlier, and someone had worked with the whole family, it might have taken a completely different turn. Someone could have strengthened the parents' competencies, worked therapeutically with both the parent and the child to show them how to communicate with each other, so the parent could understand the child's needs. But currently, there is no way to force the parent to participate"* (KP6). (KP9): *"What I missed sometimes was work with the family. That overlap. There are parents you can't always talk to, but there are also parents who would appreciate support. They had demanding children and didn't fully trust themselves in their parenting..."*.

The interconnectedness of family dynamics and children's development is described by several participants as functioning like "communicating vessels": (KP3): *"When the parents were okay, it reflected on the children as well"*. (KP4): *"We try to support the children, it's like communicating vessels, when the foster parent is supported, the child is supported too"*. *"Therapy was extended to the parents as well, they began to observe more closely what the child perceives. Until then, they thought, it's just a child, they'll forget. And after those meetings, they started realizing the child is like a sponge, absorbing sounds, impressions, they remember everything, store it all. And then it can all explode. Often the parents then stop discussing everything in front of the children, they listen to us in that, that*

the child shouldn't hear that there's no food, let them enjoy their childhood, misbehave, play..." (KP3). Housing insecurity was frequently cited as one of the most destabilizing factors affecting families' functioning and children's development: *"We always said, think of the children... but we were mostly trying to save the roof over their heads so that the children could live with dignity. And only then would you ask: do you want tutoring, to go to camp? Do you just want to talk about how you're doing? That part came only last"*. (KP3).

Such accounts reflect the cumulative nature of disadvantage that many families face. Everyday material hardship—unstable housing, limited privacy, poverty—often intersects with other forms of exclusion, such as lack of access to education, healthcare, or psychological support.

These interwoven barriers shape the lived realities of both children and parents. In working with children in vulnerable situations, professionals emphasize the necessity of tailoring support to individual needs and family contexts: *"There's no universal approach to children. It always has to be individual"* (KP1).

Establishing trust and mapping support needs is described as the core of the social work role: *"At the beginning, you have to build a relationship with the family, map out the areas where they might need support"* (KP5). *"Sometimes we get a report from the school, from the police, or the parent comes themselves, so I have to talk to the parent and the child to find out what the problem is... I try to understand the family, the child, whether the child has any other problems or whether it was a one-time incident"*. Social workers describe the work with families as complex and situated across multiple domains of everyday life: *"It was complex... The families lived in unsuitable conditions, in shelters, inadequate apartments, hostels with cockroaches and bedbugs... they didn't have their own keys to the flat, so from the beginning we were setting up many things – from social benefits to household management, self-care, even mental hygiene, and of course, we were interested in the children"* (KP8).

Within this complexity, the role of the social worker is often likened to that of a guide—supporting the family through a collaborative and voluntary process: *"Working based on voluntariness and cooperation, not as a command, more like a lay guide"*. Nonetheless, as KP3 notes, the principle of voluntariness can be compromised by structural dependencies, especially in housing services: *"SAS and Housing First are two major areas and often they clashed. Because when you're signing a voluntary agreement with the organization, it's kind of voluntary–involuntary, because thanks to the organization, you can actually have housing — it's conditional on cooperation"*.

In this context, student placements are not only a professional learning opportunity but also a window into the deep-rooted, layered disadvantages families face. Engaging directly with these realities can sharpen students' awareness of inequality and enhance their ability to respond in ways that respect complexity, dignity, and structural constraints.

Communication, Authenticity, and Transformative Relational Practice in Work with Children at Risk

In working with children at risk, communication partners emphasised that children need to feel seen, heard, and taken seriously. This was articulated through repeated calls for attentive presence: *"Even some attention, sometimes there's maybe five kids at home and then they get lost in there. They need to be seen, to be heard, to be listened to, to their needs."* (KP4). Authenticity and emotional openness were identified as key conditions for building trust, particularly in contexts where children have experienced relational ruptures and social marginalisation. KP6 noted, *"That someone understands them, listens to them, and those are the basic principles that we work on. We give these kids the space to say what's bothering them..."*

The data underscores the need to transcend formal, hierarchical roles and enter into relational encounters based on mutual respect and recognition. Communication partners described how stepping into shared humanity, *"just being there as yourself"*, creates the conditions for children to engage more openly. Humour and emotional congruence served as anchoring mechanisms for these relationships.

Boundary-setting emerged as a crucial element of ethical relational work. Rather than externally imposed, effective boundaries were co-constructed in dialogue with children. KP3: *“But let them know their boundaries and their limits, because often these children are different... they test your boundaries”*. KP4: *“It’s terribly important, vulnerable children and young people test boundaries, a lot. And it’s important to be firm about it and somehow set those boundaries for them as well, they are able to push them terribly”*. KP2: *“And on the other hand, again, be careful not to be a good friend right off the bat to have your boundary as well, because after all, there may be situations where I need to help the older one as well, so that they take it that way”*. KP5: *“More of an understanding, friendly kind of attitude, but again with some boundaries”*. KP4 talks about the benefits of setting boundaries in a participatory way with children and then respecting those boundaries: *“Setting those boundaries but in a participatory way. Even the children themselves have said what they want the rules to be. They agreed on it and took it as their own”*. *“To lead the whole group to have some respect, to respect each other and the rules in the group. It is important to give space to each of the participants to have a voice”* (KP9). Similarly, KP6 speaks of the emphasis on child/client participation, involving them in the “happenings” of the service, programme design: *“It helped me a lot to be part of a community work project that builds a lot on participatory techniques, which I still use... I started to bring more of my own authenticity, to invite those clients to participate more, and I actually used that with those clients in those growth groups and clubs”*. *“It works to involve everyone in the group, they hear themselves and not me... it’s about involving them as much as possible”* (KP7). *“I’m thinking now that it’s worked quite well to pull the kids into running the groups. I thought that was good, because it turned out that some of those kids had quite decent leadership skills... it’s terribly important for them to get feedback that they’re like useful. That they can be listened to, respected and followed but that in doing so they have a huge responsibility for the others”* (KP9). This participatory approach not only enhances children’s sense of agency but also models respectful negotiation of relational space.

Underlying these accounts is a deep commitment to recognising children as active agents—*“the forgers of their own destiny”* (KP10)—rather than passive recipients of care. This stance challenges adult-centric paradigms and foregrounds children’s voices in decisions that affect them. Such an orientation aligns with intersectional theory, which urges sensitivity to the complex, overlapping axes of disadvantage that shape children’s lives, including poverty, migration background, family instability, or racialisation. Participants highlighted the importance of not remaking or judging children, but *“taking them as they are”* (KP2), thereby counteracting dominant deficit-based narratives.

KP3’s own authenticity is important in relation to children: *“Make them very authentic... It works when you listen to them, when you come out of some of that role and you’re just there for yourself”*. KP2: *“Yeah and they know you understand it and maybe if something is not clear again you ask. He has that feeling of like that importance afterwards as well. It’s about the overall attitude as well. The person across from you is always human. He knows it...”*. KP4: *“It also definitely doesn’t work if the person is not authentic or preaches water and drinks wine. Like maybe smoking is bad and then around the corner they see him smoking”*. KP6: *“It is important for the lecturer to be authentic so that they also know that we are human and have some feelings. To react authentically in those situations”*. KP9: *“The strength I see is that there are people working there who are really interested in the children. They are people with the personality to make the children trust them, to be interested in them and to be genuine”*. A sense of humour is also important in cementing the relationship with the children according to the perception of the communication partners: KP4: *“I think it’s good to have some humour and make fun of yourself as well, that you can maybe laugh, that’s some cementing element in it”*.

From the perspective of the communication partners, being able to work with one’s own emotions is also pivotal: KP3: *“...to be kind and really to be able to work with your emotions as well, because it’s very challenging. And the kids are anxious sometimes”*. KP7: *“...to have some self-experience or training. But for them to understand themselves... to go for training, a course where they learn about themselves, so that they are prepared for what can happen, like transference relationships”*.

Towards children, according to communication partners, it is important to be empathetic, non-directive in communication, avoiding “belittling”: *“It is important to be empathetic, some belittling, mocking, directive approach, definitely not”* (KP4). *“It doesn’t work to lecture, lecture about what to do and try to educate”* (KP7). *“I personally think there is correction and moralizing in the therapeutic process. We all know why a child is at risk and why they behave the way they do. It is because he is deprived and traumatized. It doesn’t work to tell him what he’s doing wrong and why he’s doing it and that he can’t do it.”* (KP10). *“Until then maybe no one listened to them and took their opinion seriously and maybe even put them down”* (KP6). *“I try not to criticize and evaluate. Just establish a relationship and then everything will come by itself”* (KP8).

Communication partners also perceive it as important that the child feels respected: *“We take them seriously as a person too... Until then, maybe no one listened to them and took their opinion seriously... we take their needs seriously...”* (KP6). Along with respecting children’s needs and listening to them, KP10 also talks about empowering children, acknowledging that they are active “creators of their own lives”: *“I still think they lack respect. No matter how old they are, they don’t get enough respect for being the creators of their lives. The forgers of their own destiny”*. And to build/support building a sense of trust in themselves as well: *“Someone who can provide help and support”* (KP4).

According to the communication partners, it also seems to be important to perceive and respect the authenticity of the children: *“I just take the child as he is, so he sits in front of me, stands or something he did and just talk to him normally, there I show that yes I take it, they appreciate it”* (KP2). *“... to create an atmosphere in the group where the kids feel comfortable, so actually acceptance, not judging their opinions, not judging and not putting down...”* (KP6). *“Let’s not try to remake the kids, let’s take them as they are and treat them accordingly. Because a lot of parents are trying to remake those kids instead of being concerned about where that kid is and what their options are”* (KP2).

DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS FOR SOCIAL WORK

These relational principles find a powerful expression in **transformative buddying** practices. Within such programmes, children are paired with social work students, establishing sustained, trust-based relationships. Notably, these interactions are mutually developmental: while children benefit from individualised support and recognition, students report growth in self-reflexivity, interpersonal competence, and a deeper understanding of intersectional experiences. The dyadic structure of buddying thus serves as a microcosm of transformative practice—disrupting traditional hierarchies, fostering authentic connection, and nurturing critical awareness on both sides.

Through the lens of transformative and intersectional social work, these findings highlight the ethical and pedagogical potential of relational work rooted in authenticity, participation, and recognition. Especially in the context of cumulative disadvantage, such practices do not merely support individual children—they contest systemic invisibility and cultivate capacities for mutual transformation. This resonates with findings from international contexts. For example, in the UK, buddying and mentoring programmes within social work education have demonstrated similar outcomes in enhancing students’ critical engagement with systemic disadvantage (Smith, 2019). Likewise, Canadian initiatives stress the importance of relationship-based practice and the cultivation of ethical sensitivity in student training (Thibeault, Flynn, 2020). These parallels indicate a broader applicability of buddying as a pedagogical tool beyond local contexts and highlight its potential contribution to global conversations on social justice-oriented education.

The transformative nature of buddying as a relational and reflective practice in intersectional social work has crucial implications for education and practice in the field. As underscored by Gümüşcü et al. (Gümüşcü, Nygren, Khoo, 2018), social work is inherently complex, particularly in child welfare contexts. This complexity challenges traditional power dynamics and highlights the potential of buddying to **establish trust-based relationships**. Such relationships enable transformative encounters, allowing students to engage deeply with the lived realities of children facing multiple

intersections of disadvantage, further enhancing the recognition of ethical engagement (Onalu, Okoye, 2021). This relational aspect fosters not just academic learning but a critical engagement with social justice, aligning closely with the core tenets of social work as a discipline committed to equity. Moreover, the idea of mutual learning through buddying necessitates a re-evaluation of social work curricula. Dahal (2022) discusses how transformative education practices advocate for equity and empowerment, mirroring the goals of buddying. When students actively participate in their learning through reflective practices like journaling and dialogical engagement, they develop the necessary relational and ethical competencies to navigate the complexities identified by Wu et al. (2021).

The importance of *self-reflection in social work training* has been reinforced by studies advocating for structured reflective tools within the curriculum, providing students the scaffolding to build their professional identities (Onalu, Okoye, 2021; Dahal, 2022). However, the success of such reflective practices is contingent upon institutional support and the willingness of educators to critically engage with students' positionalities. Without intentional scaffolding and a safe learning environment, the risk of superficial reflection remains (Brookfield, 2017). This calls for a nuanced implementation that avoids tokenistic approaches to self-reflexivity. Consequently, integrating these practices into social work education is not merely beneficial but essential for cultivating informed and empathetic practitioners. Children's participation is paramount within the buddying model and must be recognized as a right and a resource—this elevates their agency and aligns with the principles of social justice taught in many advanced social work programs (Onalu, Okoye, 2021).

The involvement of children in their own narratives and experiences enhances the authenticity of relational practices between students' and children's lived realities. As articulated by Mosiara (2023), education plays a critical role in empowering marginalized groups and promoting equity, thus advocating for children's involvement in the processes affecting their lives aligns with this broader educational mandate. Institutional transformations are also necessary to bridge the theory-practice divide in social work education. Collaborations such as those outlined by Archer-Kuhn et al. (2020) during the COVID-19 pandemic highlight the essential need for institutions to adapt their education methods while maintaining relevance to real-world complexities. The partnerships should involve community stakeholders and field practitioners to create experiential learning opportunities reflecting the realities students will face in their careers. Implementing buddying not only serves to enhance students' understanding of social injustices but also fosters the capacity to enact change within their communities upon entering the workforce. Nevertheless, structural constraints within academic institutions—such as limited time for supervision, overloaded curricula, and uneven field placement quality—can significantly hinder the transformative potential of buddying. As noted by Beddoe & Staniforth (2021), unless embedded within a coherent institutional strategy, even the most innovative practices may fail to shift entrenched power imbalances or produce lasting impact. Thus, critical evaluation of institutional readiness remains a necessary step.

The buddying models, particularly those integrating reflective tools with direct engagement, have been shown to support personal growth and the broader objectives of social work education. As stated by Yearwood (Yearwood, Barbera, Fisher et al., 2021), educators hold the moral responsibility to impart knowledge that confronts systemic oppression. This obligation can be fulfilled by embedding innovative methodologies into social work training frameworks. This sentiment aligns with the findings of Bussey, Jemal and Caliste (2020), advocating for a radical transformation of social work methodologies, where approaches like buddying embody the critical consciousness necessary for advancing social justice.

In conclusion, buddying embodies a transformative intersectional practice within social work education. It not only enriches the lived experiences of both students and children but reinforces a broader social justice agenda critical to the profession's identity. As the findings advocate, it is imperative for social work curricula to embrace relational competencies, recognize children

as vital participants in their narratives, and foster institutional collaborations that solidify these transformative practices within the educational framework.

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